

Acid Dissociation Constants of some *N*-Aryl-Hydroxamic Acids in Mixed Solvents.

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The acid dissociation constants of a number of *N*-aryl-hydroxamic acids have been determined by Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique in 50% v/v dioxane-water and in 50% v/v ethanol-water media of ionic strength of 0.1M (NaClO₄) and at 25° ± 0.1°. The results have been interpreted in terms of factors which have bearing on the acid dissociation constants.

ALTHOUGH several studies have been reported¹ for chelating properties of *N*-aryl-hydroxamic acids, relatively very little work appears to have been carried out on the physicochemical properties of these structurally similar compounds. It was therefore thought worthwhile to undertake a systematic study of the effect of substitution in some of these reagents on their dissociation and on the stability of their metal chelates. The present paper describes the determination of acid dissociation constants of *N*-benzoyl-phenylhydroxylamine (*N*-BPHA), *N*-cinnamoyl-phenylhydroxylamine (*N*-CPHA), *N*-benzoyl-*p*-tolylhydroxylamine (*N*-*B* (*p*) THA), *N*-benzoyl-*o*-tolylhydroxylamine (*N*-*B* (*o*)THA), *N*-*o*-iodo benzoyl-phenylhydroxylamine (*N*-*o*-iodo-BP-HA), *N*-2, 4-dichloro-benzoyl-phenylhydroxylamine (*N*-2, 4-dichloro-BPHA), *N*-2-furoyl-phenylhydroxylamine (*N*-2-FPHA), *N*-2 thenoyl-phenylhydroxylamine (*N*-2-TPHA), *N*-cyclohexanoyl-phenylhydroxylamine (*N*-CHPHA) and *N*-acetyl-phenylhydroxylamine (*N*-APHA) by Calvin-Bjerrum^{5,6} potentiometric titration technique as a necessary prelude to their chelation studies.

Experimental

Materials : The reagents used in this work were prepared as described earlier¹. Dioxane was purified by Weissberger's method⁷ and was freshly distilled before use. Lime distilled ethanol was further distilled after refluxing with metallic sodium. Sodium perchlorate (Riedel) was used to maintain constant ionic strength, $\mu = 0.1$. Standard solutions of carbonate-free sodium hydroxide (E. Merk) and perchloric acid (E. Merk) were prepared in the conventional way. Redistilled water was used in all measurements and preparation of solutions.

Apparatus : All pH measurements were made with a Cambridge bench type pH-meter equipped with a glass-saturated calomel electrode pair and standardized with buffer solutions at pH 4.00 and 9.00. The design of the water-jacketed titrating vessel was such as to allow nitrogen (pre-saturated with solvents) through the reaction mixture during the whole course of titration. Water was circulated through the jacket of the titrating vessel from a electrically maintained thermostat to maintain constant temperature at 25° ± 0.1°. Magnetic stirrer was used to stir the reaction mixture.

The Acid Dissociation Constants : For each reagent, duplicate titrations were carried out adopting Calvin-Bjerrum method. This included titrations of perchloric acid (5.0×10^{-4} moles) + reagent (2.0×10^{-4} moles) against standard solution of sodium hydroxide (0.1M). The initial volume of the solution was 100 ml containing 50% v/v dioxane-water or 50% v/v ethanol-water. The titration was started with the addition of equal volumes of base and dioxane or ethanol with necessary increments depending on the rate of change of pH of the reaction mixture. The pH of the reaction mixture was recorded as a function of base after the attainment of each equilibrium. pH-meter readings were corrected for using mixed solvents^{8,9}.

Calculations

The reagents studied in the present work are weak acids of the type HR. The acid dissociation constant, K_{OH} was calculated from the experimental points in the buffer region using the equation (concentration sign, square bracket was omitted for clarity) :

$$K_{OH} = \frac{H^+ \cdot S}{T_R - S}$$

where, S = H⁺ + Na⁺ - OH⁻ - A

T_R and A were the total reagent and perchloric acid concentrations, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The acid dissociation constants, pK of different reagents determined in this work in 50% v/v dioxane-water and in 50% v/v ethanol-water media are summarized in Table 1. Table 1 shows that the observed pK

TABLE 1—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF *N*-ARYL HYDROXAMIC ACIDS

Hydroxamic acids	μ = 0.1M (NaClO ₄) t = 25° ± 0.1°	
	50% v/v dioxane-water medium*	50% v/v ethanol-water medium.
<i>N</i> -CPHA	10.23	10.02
<i>N</i> -CHPHA	10.19	10.00
<i>N</i> - <i>B</i> (<i>p</i>) THA	10.17	9.95
<i>N</i> - <i>B</i> (<i>o</i>) THA	10.09	9.86
<i>N</i> -BPHA	10.05	9.80
<i>N</i> -2-TPHA	9.88	9.70
<i>N</i> - <i>o</i> -iodo-BPHA	9.77	9.59
<i>N</i> -APHA	9.77	9.56
<i>N</i> -2-FPHA	9.60	9.41
<i>N</i> -2,4-dichloro-BPHA	9.51	9.30

* The error limit is ± 0.02.

value of any reagent in dioxane-water medium is higher than its corresponding value in ethanol-water medium. This is consistent with the fact that the former solvent-pair medium has lower dielectric constant which increases the electrostatic forces between the ions and facilitates formation of molecular species.

The experimental pK values of the parent compound, *N*-BPHA and its analogues indicate that they are very weak acids. The relative order of increasing pK of these reagents obtained is N -CPHA $>$ N -CHPHA $>$ N -*B*(*p*) THA $>$ N -*B*(*o*) THA $>$ N -BPHA $>$ N -2-TPHA $>$ N -*o*-iodo-BPHA, N -APHA $>$ N -2-FPHA $>$ N -2, 4-dichloro-BPHA. The relatively small difference among pK values of various compounds, which is, in certain cases almost within the range of experimental error raises some doubt as to the significance that could be attached to it. Nevertheless, the data do reflect the trend in the acid strength of these structurally similar hydroxamic acids.

N-CPHA is a weaker acid than *N*-BPHA. This may be attributed to the depleted inductive effect of C=O function for withdrawing the lone pair on nitrogen of \ddot{N} -OH group since (δ^+) character of the carbonyl carbon is decreased due to supply of electron from the nearby double bond.

The compound *N*-CHPHA differs from *N*-BPHA in having a cyclohexyl group instead of a phenyl group as is present in *N*-BPHA. The latter compound (*N*-BPHA) will exhibit more acidic character due to the presence of the phenyl group which exerts $-I$ effect. This effect assists the anion stabilisation of *N*-BPHA more than that of the compound *N*-CHPHA since the latter contains a cyclohexyl group which has less $-I$ effect. Therefore the anion stabilising effect will be less pronounced in the case of *N*-CHPHA.

The measured pK values of *N*-*B*(*o*) THA and *N*-*B*(*p*) THA show that they are both slightly weaker acids than *N*-BPHA. The weaker acid character of the former two compounds than the latter is due to $+I$ effect (electron pushing) of substituted methyl group. It can thus increase the electron density on nitrogen of \ddot{N} -OH function and consequently decrease the ionisation of these hydroxamic acids. Among the ortho-tolyl and para-tolyl compounds, the former has higher acid strength, though the value is very close to that of the latter. It should be slightly stronger acid since methyl group in ortho-compound is placed closer to the ionisation site and may influence the ionisation by steric interaction¹⁰. The data (Table 1) obtained support this prediction.

N-*o*-iodo-BPHA is a stronger acid than *N*-BPHA. This is quite obvious since iodo group has $-I$ effect (electron attracting) on the lone pair of hydroxylamine nitrogen and thus facilitates ionisation. Moreover, iodo group is expected to have smaller acid strengthening effect due to its location in ortho position to the

reacting group. Similar electronic effect as above but with greater magnitude is observed in 2,4-dichloro-BPHA. Here both chlorine groups exert joint $-I$ effect on electron density of hydroxylamine nitrogen, which makes it stronger acid than *N*-*o*-iodo-BPHA by stabilising the anion of the acid.

The acid dissociation constants, pK values of both *N*-2-FPHA and *N*-2-TPHA are lower than the corresponding value of the parent compound, *N*-BPHA. The enhanced acidity of the former two hydroxamic acids is due to the presence of electronegative oxygen and sulphur atoms in their respective 5-membered heterocyclic ring, which increase the stability of the anionic form of the acids via $-I$ mechanism. Since oxygen is more electronegative than sulphur, it imposes greater electron deficiency on hydroxylamine nitrogen, and hence anion stabilisation of *N*-2-FPHA is relatively increased. Thus *N*-2-FPHA is found to be stronger acid than *N*-2-TPHA.

The experimental pK of *N*-APHA is lower than the corresponding value of *N*-BPHA. This observation may cause some surprise since phenyl group is generally considered a more electron attractor than the methyl group. But it should be remembered that the benzene ring, despite its negative inductive effect, is conjugated with C=O group in *N*-BPHA, and may donate π -electron density to it through conjugation. The conjugate effects of this type are absent in *N*-APHA molecule and as a consequence of this the depletion of (δ^+) character of the carbonyl carbon is not experienced here.

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